

GROWTH PERIOD AND PRODUCTIVITY INDICATORS OF CHICKPEAS VARIETIES AND LINES IN THE CONTROL VARIETY TRIAL NURSERY GROWN IN REINFIELD AREAS

¹Musirmanov Dilshod Yesirgapovich, ²Rustam Xasan Jiyanqul o‘g‘li

¹qishloq xo‘jaligi fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori, katta ilmiy xodim

²(PhD) tayanch doktorant

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Аннотация. Мазкур мақола лалмикор майдонларда етиштирилаётган нўхат нав ва тизмаларнинг ўсув даври давомийлиги ва махсулдорлик кўрсаткичига ижобий таъсир этадиган бир туп ўсимлик хосили ва дуккак ичидаги донлар сони кўрсаткичи бўйича келтириб ўтилган ва танлаш ишлари амалга оширилган.

Калим сўзлар: нўхат экин, нав ва тизмалар, дуккаклар сони, бир туп ўсимлик хосили, униб чиқиш, ўсув даври.

Abstract. In this article, the chickpea cultivars and ridges grown in reinfield areas, which have a positive effect on the duration of the growing season and the productivity index, are cited and selected according to the indicator of the number of grains in the pod and the plant yield.

Keywords: chickpea crop, variety and rows, number of pods, yield per plant, germination, growth period.

Аннотация. В данной статье приведены и отобраны по показателю количества зерен в бобе сорта нута и гряды, выращиваемые в засушливых районах, которые положительно влияют на продолжительность вегетационного периода и показатель продуктивности.

Ключевые слова: урожай нута, сорт и ряды, количество стручков, урожайность с растения, всхожесть, период роста.

As a result of sudden changes in the climate in the world in recent years, during the development stage of the studied chickpea crop, due to the high temperature rise, frost, damage by diseases and pests, it has a negative effect on the grain quality indicator, causing a sharp decrease in productivity. In order to prevent these situations, one of the tasks before the world's leading breeding scientists is to create starting materials for practical selection using early, biotic and abiotic factors resistant, competitive varieties and lines of chickpeas and to create new varieties based on them.

S. Özer [1] and Çelik, İ [2] in their scientific research, chickpeas are consumed as food preserves, flour products, boiled and steamed due to their high enzyme content.

According to Z.U. Nisa et.al [3] experiments, Pakistan ranks third in the world for the cultivation of chickpeas. Among all the provinces, Punjab accounts for 80 percent of the chickpea production in Pakistan. It is mainly grown in marginal lands, irrigated and semi-arid fields.

V.V. Balashov [4] stated that chickpea varieties created in semi-desert conditions are adapted to give high yields even in drought conditions.

O.G. Saipov indicated that the energy of germination in pea seeds increases as the seeds develop. This enhancement in germination energy contributes significantly to the improvement of field fertility, even during cool spring conditions.

The research focused on assessing the number of pods per plant and the number of grains per pod in relation to the length of the growing season and the productivity index of various chickpea varieties and samples.

The study examined various chickpea varieties and ridges, which were planted in groups of 20 with 3 repetitions across an area of 10 m². Germination for the chickpea varieties occurred between March 27 and March 30. The results indicated that the number of sprouted plants ranged from 82 to 95, while the number of fully matured plants was between 53 and 73. Full ripening of the plants took place between June 19 and July 1 (table 1).

table 1

Growth period duration and yield index of chickpea varieties and ridges (Gallaorol-2024 year)

Plot	Entry	Name	Germination, date	The number of sprouted plants, pcs	The number of fully ripe plants, pcs	Ripe, date	Vegetation period, days	The number of pods in one plant, pcs				The number of grains in one plant, pcs	One plant yield, g
								1 grainy	2 grainy	3 grainy	Total		
1	1	Yulduz(l.check)	29 mar	87	72	23 june	87	37	17		54	70	22,0
2	6	FLIP13-129C	28 mar	85	53	1 july	95	38	9		47	57	18,6
3	11	FLIP13-264C	28 mar	92	71	22 june	86	59	13	5	77	101	27,2
4	16	FLIP13-377C	29 mar	88	68	1 july	94	38	7		46	54	19,4
5	2	FLIP13-84C	27 mar	82	73	21 june	86	70	13		82	95	27,5
6	7	FLIP13-130C	28 mar	95	60	30 june	94	31	12		42	54	19,8
7	12	FLIP13-293C	27 mar	93	71	19 june	84	73	16	1	91	109	26,2
8	17	FLIP13-384C	28 mar	95	60	29 june	93	54	10		64	74	18,6
9	3	FLIP13-96C	27 mar	94	71	26 june	91	54	10		64	75	18,1
10	8	FLIP13-141C	27 mar	86	63	30 june	95	46	10		56	66	9,7
11	13	FLIP13-344C	30 mar	85	72	23 june	85	55	17	3	74	96	26,1
12	18	FLIP 82-150C	28 mar	84	57	30 june	94	56	14		70	85	21,2
13	4	FLIP13-125C	28 mar	83	70	24 june	88	50	9	1	60	71	24,9
14	9	FLIP13-142C	27 mar	83	58	28 june	93	58	10		68	78	12,1
15	14	FLIP13-363C	28 mar	88	73	23 june	86	61	18	1	80	100	27,0

16	19	FLIP88-85C	27 mar	95	66	22 june	87	71	20	6	96	127	25,4
17	5	FLIP13-126C	30 mar	92	63	22 june	84	54	8	3	65	79	30,6
18	10	FLIP13-165C	28 mar	95	69	22 june	86	64	9	1	74	85	28,2
19	15	FLIP13-370C	27 mar	87	71	23 june	87	79	15	3	96	116	29,0
20	20	FLIP93-93C	27 mar	87	73	23 june	88	72	11	3	86	103	27,8
		Min	27 mar	82	53	19 june	84	31	7	1	42	54	9,7
		Mean	28 mar	89	67	25 june	89	56	12	3	70	85	23,0
		Max	30 mar	95	73	1 july	95	79	20	6	96	127	30,6
		LSD₀₅					2,11						
		LSD_{05 %}					2,364						
		S					1,305						
		Cv %					1,5						

The growing period of the plants ranged from 84 to 95 days, with the Yulduz variety specifically taking 87 days to mature. Among the other tested varieties, FLIP13-293C and FLIP13-126C had the shortest growth periods of 84 days, while FLIP13-344C took 85 days. The remaining varieties, including FLIP13-264C, FLIP13-84C, FLIP13-363C, and FLIP13-165C, also ripened earlier than the Yulduz variety, demonstrating a trend of early maturation in this group.

The total number of pods per plant ranged from 42 to 96 pods. For the standard Yulduz variety, the average was 54 pods. Additionally, it was observed that 16 ridges produced between 10 to 40 pods more than the standard variety. This indicates that some of the ridges achieved pod counts significantly higher than the standard Yulduz variety.

The observations indicate that the number of grains obtained from a single bush varies between 54 and 127 grains across different varieties. The yield index per plant is noted as 97.30.6 grams. In comparison to the standard Yulduz variety, which has a yield of 22.0 grams, several other samples demonstrate higher yields: the FLIP13-126C sample yields 30.6 grams, FLIP13-370C yields 29.0 grams, FLIP13-165C yields 28.2 grams, and FLIP93-93C yields 27.8 grams. These results suggest that the tested samples outperform the standard variety, indicating a positive outcome in terms of yield.

The selection of chickpea varieties and samples was conducted based on productive character indicators, which demonstrated a positive correlation with both the length of the growing season and productivity. A total of 6 samples were chosen for their high pod yield index in comparison to the standard variety. Additionally, recommendations for planting were provided as part of the selection process.

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